

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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Workshop Report

“Pushing Accelerator Frontiers network galvanizes extreme storage-ring community and beyond” – Highlights of the iFAST WP5 Extreme Storage Rings Workshop (ESRW22)

WP5.2 Pushing Accelerator Frontiers

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ABSTRACT

The iFAST ESRW22 workshop was organized from 31 January to 8 February 2022 in virtual space. The purpose of this workshop was to bring together experts from several areas of physics that push storage rings to “extreme use”, and storage-ring accelerator experts. Precision experiments as g-2 and EDM were covered in addition to ultra-low emittance light sources, future hadron accelerators, and novel concepts such as quantum computers based on stored beams, and Gamma Factories. Also participating in this meeting were experts of lepton and hadron storage rings, who addressed topics of advanced cooling, crystalline beams, and innovative beam diagnostics.

I.FAST Consortium, 2022

For more information on I.FAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

- 1. INTRODUCTION.....3
- 2. STATE OF THE ART OF STORAGE RINGS.....5
- 3. LIMITS AND PROSPECTS FOR FUTURE LEPTON AND HADRON STORAGE RINGS.....7
- 4. PRECISION EXPERIMENTS WITH STORAGE RINGS8
- 5. BEAM STABILIZATION AND DIAGNOSTICS9
- 6. APPLICATIONS OF MACHINE LEARNING..... 10
- 7. CRYSTALLINE BEAMS AND QUANTUM COMPUTERS BASED ON STORED BEAMS 11
- 8. ADVANCED COOLING AND THE GAMMA FACTORY 13
- 9. FINAL DISCUSSION AND EPILOGUE 14

1. Introduction

In times of COVID restrictions and virtual events, the Task “Pushing the Accelerator Frontiers” (PAF) of the iFAST project set a new standard for community meetings. Speaker invitations with a short 3 weeks’ notice did not scare, but rather intrigued the storage-ring community, with the result that the forward-looking “Extreme Storage Rings Workshop” (ESRW22) was marked by a robust participation, as is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Time evolution of participant registrations for the iFAST ESRW22.

The purpose of ESRW22 was to bring together experts from several areas of physics that push storage rings to "extreme use", and storage-ring accelerator experts. This goal was successfully met. A noticeable feature of this particular accelerator physics workshop was the participation by many experimentalists, which have been “sparked” by a call of Mieczyslaw Witold Krasny through the channels of the Gamma Factory community. The seven sessions of ESRW22 captured the latest state-of-the-art of all kinds of storage rings for lepton and hadron beams with a variety of diverse purposes. High-precision experiments such as g-2 and EDM were reviewed alongside ultra-low emittance light sources, future hadron accelerators, and novel concepts such as quantum computers based on stored cold beams and Gamma factories. Experts of lepton and hadron storage rings addressed novel cooling techniques, crystalline beams, and advanced beam diagnostics.

The event was attended by 150 expert participants hailing from a large number of laboratories and universities: Stony Brook University, US (5); JLU Giessen, Germany (1); Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland (2); LPNHE Sorbonne University Paris, France (1); MPIK GSI (1); University of Ferrara, Italy (1); National Institute of Radiation Science and Technologies (NIRS), Japan (1); A. Alikhanyan National Laboratory, Armenia (1); ALBA-CELLS, Spain (2); ANL & NIU, USA (3); Albert Ludwigs University Freiburg (1); Budker INP (4); Brookhaven National Laboratory (4); CEA

Paris-Saclay and Paris-Saclay U/ (1); CERN (13); CNRS / IJCLAB (4); Cockcroft Institute / University of Liverpool (1); Cornell University and BNL, USA (1); DESY, Germany (8); Diamond Light Source, UK (1); ELI-NP - IFIN-HH (1); ESRF (1); ETH Zurich (6); FH Aachen, Germany (4); Fermilab, USA (1); FZ Jülich / RWTH Aachen (6); GSI, Germany (23); Goethe University Frankfurt (2); HI-Jena (1); Helmholtz Institut Mainz (1); INFN-LNF (2); INR RAS (2); ISIS/RAL/STFC (2); Indiana University (1); KEK, Japan (1); KIT, Germany (11); Landau Institute for Theoretical Physics (1); Los Alamos National Laboratory (1); Mapna (1); Max Planck Institute for Nuclear Physics (1); Michigan State University (1); Nihon University, Japan (1); NIU (1); Paul Scherrer Institute (5); RAL and Oxford University (2); RIKEN (1); SLAC (3); SSRF/SARI (1); Sandia National Labs (1); Synchrotron SOLEIL (2); Tsinghua University (3); University of Liverpool (1); University of Oxford (1); and University of Washington (1).

2. State of the art of storage rings

In the **first session** (see Fig. 2), the **state of the art of lepton storage-ring colliders** was unveiled by Naoko Iida from KEK, who discussed the high-intensity low-emittance positron injector as a key to high luminosity in SuperKEKB top-up operation. The reverse bends (RB) of the SuperKEKB damping ring also is an intriguing option for future light sources. The state of the art of synchrotron light sources was reviewed by Simon White of ESRF, while PSI's Masamitsu discussed injection challenges for lowest-emittance storage-ring based light sources. Concerning ultimate light sources, whether the next step will be Hybrid LGB-RB MBA or 19BA lattices, or a complex bend optics was left open. The trend to on-axis injection and development of ultrafast kickers was emphasized. Only another gain by about a factor of ten in emittance is required to reach the diffraction limit, and there is no need to go below 10 pm emittance values in future light sources.

Figure 2: A snapshot of the first session on zoom.

The state of **hadron storage rings** was introduced by Markus Steck of GSI, reporting that in the ESR ion-beam emittances can be pushed to values of order 100 fm and momentum spread down to 10^{-7} , thanks to stochastic and electron cooling. The GSI storage ring ESR can even produce *ordered* beams for intensities below ~ 1000 ions. These beams are characterized, during cooling, by a sudden reduction in phase space by 4-5 orders of magnitude. Ions can be decelerated from 400 to 4 MeV/u and then further to 6 keV/u. At GSI the ESR storage ring passes beams to the CRYRing storage ring, which then delivers these beams further to the HITRAP, where highly charged ions are cooled and trapped in the Penning trap at a vacuum of 10^{-12} mbar. Giulio Stancari of Fermilab reported on the

state of the investigations in the IOTA facility (Fig. 3), a primary goal of which is the experimental demonstration that a highly nonlinear integrable optics will/may enhance beam stability. The presentation highlighted another result. Namely, after 30 years of attempts, at IOTA the new technique of optical stochastic cooling (and in 3D) was demonstrated for the very first time. The audience was mesmerized by the results of synchrotron radiation studies from a single electron! The final discussion of this session raised an ambiguous aspect of the accelerator and storage rings R&D, summarized by the question: “is it the accelerator physics community that should push the accelerator frontier and then offer to the community of experimenters the *best-beam of now*, or are the needs of the experimentalists the driving motivation for pushing the frontiers?” Regarding this dilemma, the accelerator audience opined that the community needs at least 2-3 facilities devoted to beam physics development and beam diagnostics. At the same time, the experimenters’ community, through a comment of Witek Krasny, launched the idea of optical stochastic cooling for a fully stripped Ca ion beam in the LHC, to realize an isoscalar HL-LHC collider!

Figure 3: The first experimental demonstration of optical stochastic cooling was reported from the IOTA facility at FNAL.

3. Limits and prospects for future lepton and hadron storage rings

The **Second Session** of the workshop was devoted to exploring the **limits and prospects for future lepton and hadron storage rings**. The future FAIR “Collector Ring” (CR) and the HESR were reviewed by Oleksiy Dolinsky and Jan Hetzel, both from GSI. The features of the FAIR CR were reviewed, in particular, the dynamic modification of slip factor during cooling for optimum efficiency. The CR will operate as a mass spectrometer with 10^{-6} resolution, aided by a nonlinear corrector. The High Energy Storage Ring (HESR) will operate Pbar and heavy-ion beams and its operation in the FAIR facility will make use of longitudinal stacking. In tests, the inversion of HESR magnet polarity proved reproducible and comparable! Further R&D for consolidating the HESR components and concepts will be carried on at the COSY storage rings at FZJ.

At the frontier of future lepton storage rings, Renkai Li from Tsinghua U. argued that steady-state micro-bunching ring (SSMB) will combine the high repetition rate of storage rings with the high peak power of Free Electron Lasers at a relatively low cost. This innovative concept is advanced through a solid R&D program and supported by an emerging new collaboration. SOLEIL’s Alexis Gamelin reported that present efforts push the SC harmonic cavity beyond “ $\xi=1$ ” and that key experiments demonstrated a good vacuum with a small NEG coated beam pipe. Remarkably, in Grenoble, the new ESRF-EBS facility exceeded all design goals more than 1 year ahead of schedule. Pantaleo Raimondi from SLAC reviewed the design and challenges of the 4th generation of light sources. He presented the innovative H6BA and H9BA lattices that will enable quantum leaps in SR light sources (Fig. 4). Impressively, the new approach to realize ultralow emittance beams also increases the Touschek lifetime. The discussion at this session indicated that a diffraction-limited storage ring is now well within reach!

Figure 4: Emittance (vertical axis), beam lifetime (colour), and dynamic aperture (size of circle) for present and future light source – four ultimate light source designs were proposed (H6BA*8, SSRLX, PEP H6BA, and PETRA IV) – from Pantaleo Raimond and Simone Liuzzo.

4. Precision experiments with storage rings

The **Third Session** of the workshop was devoted to **precision experiments with storage rings**. The emphasis here was on the FNAL **G-2** experiment and on the quest for measuring the electric dipole moment (**EDM**) of elementary particles. From KAIST IBS, Zhanibek Omarov discussed a new lattice concept, which promises to be less sensitive to quadrupole misalignments and hence may provide a slower spin decoherence. The electric and magnetic sextupole “combo” vastly improves spin coherence time (SCT). Frank Rathmann of FZ Julich reported that the EDM research at COSY has achieved SCTs beyond anybody’s expectations. The feedback on spin-phase with respect to Wien filter RF is a promising tool, also demonstrated at FZJ’s COSY. The next step foresees the development of a prototype EDM storage ring (PTR), which will be carried out in the frame of an EU Design Study. CERN’s Christian Carli showed that the expected EDM signal is of order 1-2 nrad/s, which highlights the importance of long decoherence time and the role of the systematic effects. He also noted that a residual magnetic field of 10^{-17} Tesla can mimic the EDM effect. The next precision experiment presented in the workshop were those of the famous G-2 campaign at Fermilab. David Tarazona from the University of Liverpool presented details of the Muon G-2 ring, where passive and active shimming achieved a field uniformity of 50 ppm. He listed the various systematic errors, and the various improvements for G-2 expected in Run 5. The discussion in this session was fired by an emotional wind. Comparing the degree of difficulties in the EDM vs. G-2 experiments was suggested and discussed, revealing divergent points of view. Intriguing novel options were suggested such as conceiving a G-2 measurement with intense CW muon beams of low-momentum spread from a Gamma Factory (GF). Dmitry Budker from JGU Mainz and UC Berkeley highlighted that the Gamma Factory will offer various “tabletop physics” at the LHC! For example, polarization by optical pumping – both electronic & nuclear polarization – will be possible at the GF, alongside other intriguing options such as GF-based EDM measurements. Indeed, the realm of precision physics enabled by the proposed GF at CERN is reminiscent of “Galileo and the telescope”.

Observation of $p_y(t)$ with two stored bunches: **Signal and pilot bunch**

► **Signal bunch**

► **Pilot bunch**

Figure 5: Bunch-selective spin manipulation and decoherence at COSY (Frank Rathmann)

5. Beam stabilization and diagnostics

The **Fourth Session** of the workshop addressed beam stabilization, Schottky signals, and diagnostics. From Shanghai Synchrotron Radiation Facility, Yongbin Leng discussed applications of the bunch-by-bunch diagnostic system. Emphasis was put on measuring the six-dimensional distribution (mean and rms) bunch-by-bunch with a “High-speed Oscilloscope based Three-dimensional bunch Charge and Position measurement system”. An associated portable software package from SSRF is available for wider usage. Laura Torino from ALBA reviewed beam instrumentation for 4th generation light sources, highlighting that these facilities require better emittance measurement and improved orbit feedback. A key issue is how to extract, from the ring beamline, the SR light needed for diagnostics (e.g., pinhole camera). At these 4th generation light sources, “everything comes back to stability!”. This is the reason why, for the SOLEIL Upgrade, reviewed by Nicolas Hubert, a closed-orbit control of better than 50 nm rms, with a bandwidth up to 1 kHz, will be implemented together with a beam-size measurement at 100 Hz. X-ray Fresnel diffraction techniques should give resolution on the micron scale. Irina Petrushina, from Stony Brook, discussed the status of the coherent electron cooling studies. A newly identified plasma-cascade instability (Fig. 6) will be harnessed for Coherent electron Cooling. A time-resolved diagnostics beam-line with 1 ps time resolution allows detailed studies of this novel cooling technique.

Figure 6: Schematic of plasma cascade instability (Irina Petrushina)

6. Applications of machine learning

Another “hot” session at the Extreme Storage Rings Workshop was devoted to the applications of machine learning for improved storage ring performance and precision experiments. In this **Fifth Session**, Simone Liuzzo of ESRF presented the “EBS Simulator” concept presently used in conjunction with the TANGO control system. Here, the electron beam is replaced by software! This approach allows testing controls software while the machine is running. The new paradigm was expressed, at the workshop, by the sentence “Everyone is dreaming of digital twins!”. Further envisaged ML applications range from accelerator design to offline data analysis. CERN’s Verena Kain presented the state of the art of ML implementation in the LHC accelerator chain. The LHC collimator setup time could be greatly reduced thanks to ML techniques: 79 collimators are now set up in 50 minutes (Fig. 7). ML can be used for predicting time series data, hence for achieving hysteresis control, e. g. for variable SPS cycling. Another ML development path is expected to increase the efficiency and flexibility of CERN accelerators. The participants brainstormed on the possibility that ML may be used for machine safety and possibly even for personal protection – which might be crossing a boundary. Self-driving cars and Boeing MAX were cited as illustrative examples. Alexander Scheinker of Los Alamos addressed ML from a conceptual point of view. He asked “What is the difference between statistics and machine learning?”. A tantalizing answer to this question was “Funding!”. A second answer was an invitation to the audience: “Everybody should come and visit Los Alamos”. One limit of machine learning is related to the difficulty of the algorithms in resolving time-varying systems. Robust machine learning for time-varying systems needs adaptive feedback. As a successful implementation, Alexander Scheinker demonstrated the ability of ML to predict the 6D phase space at FACET-II. The discussion following this presentation intrigued the audience, speakers, and organizers. SLAC’s Daniel Ratner discussed the distinction between predictive tasks and optimization tasks, along with the benefits of employing a Bayesian optimization to find a global optimum. Several subjects were put on the table, ranging from the “infoBAX” algorithm, which optimizes any function of different data, e.g., for emittance optimization, to the “badger”, namely SLAC’s version of “GeOF”. During the discussion, experts agreed that ML surrogates can be millions of times faster than explicit simulations, and may be updated directly on data. Related concepts are Ghost imaging and Fellget’s multiplex advantage. Exploiting natural laser jitter was cited as one specific application. An example of ML success was the optimization of the multi-turn injection efficiency of LEIR. Despite great confidence in ML methods, the audience concurred that supplementing ML with physics models can lead to better performance. More examples were mentioned, such as the Deep Mind and controlling plasma in a tokamak, with reinforcement learning. Lastly, the important sociological aspect of the impact of machine learning was discussed. Presently, some operators at CERN may perceive ML as a competitor; however, it was argued that when ML takes over heavy tasks from the operators, these operators will obtain more space for further development. The discussion did not address what types of development could be foreseen.

Figure 7: Improved LHC collimator setup time thanks to machine learning (Verena Kain).

7. Crystalline beams and quantum computers based on stored beams

The **Sixth Session** walked through a mixed territory of crystalline beams and quantum computers based on stored beams. Kevin Brown from Brookhaven National Lab reviewed the tantalizing prospect of realizing a quantum computer with the ions trapped in a storage ring (Fig. 8). Past studies showed that the imaginary gamma transition lattice allows crystals at high energy for reaching the goal to optimize Qubit throughput and reach maximum stability. The presentation recalled the concept of circular RFQ ion trap, first proposed by A. Ruggiero, and that 1D Doppler laser cooling cannot cool below ~ 1 mK. Though the entanglement of ions in traps had already been reached, the transition from traps to storage rings will be a crucial next step. Namely, the entanglement of trapped ions is proven, but the entanglement of stored ions is yet to be shown. It was argued that the use of storage rings for quantum information systems (QIS) is a viable and, perhaps, even necessary technology, but cautioned that QIS with relativistic beams is a new topic. So are polarized crystalline beams, and whether these could be of use. Up to now a spin coherence time of 1-10 s achieved. The Lamb-Dicke regime enables crystalline beams. The rich experience with crystalline beam studies at the PALLAS facility in Munich was revisited, acknowledging that the transverse beam temperature at PALLAS had still been 10,000 times higher than required for quantum computation (QC). Finally, the initial use of IOTA and/or a dedicated storage ring for early QIS tests were proposed. Ultimately, a proper accelerator platform to address all the challenges of storage-ring-based quantum computers will be necessary. In a moment of euphoria, it was stated: “Every physicist should have a Paul trap on his/her desk!”

Timur Shaftan, also from BNL, followed with a stimulating presentation that explored the details of accelerator-based quantum computing from a theoretical perspective. He pinned down the key elements of the QC challenges. Creating a storage-ring quantum computer requires very cold crystalline beams. The main advantage of such a system would be the large qubit capacity. Ring ion

traps are well suited for future QC applications requiring high ion capacity. Steps in this direction were set by PALLAS, Sandia micro-structured ion trap, a toroidal trap at Brigham Young University, and a trap on a microchip at UC Berkeley. Timur Shaftan observed that the accelerator community already possesses a wealth of expertise in highly precise manipulations with beams in storage rings. The challenges and needs for the future accelerator R&D are the following: 1) production of much colder beams than those available today and learning how to sustain their low temperature in steady-state; 2) advancing the storage ring technologies to reduce the amount of thermal and RF noise; 3) developing compact and highly accurate diagnostics and control systems for the ion crystals' orbit around the macroscopic ring; 4) establishing novel protocols for two-qubit and multi-qubit gates involving ultrafast pulsed lasers; 5) designing and building a broadband modulator capable of handling the large optical power of such lasers while generating short pulses with high RF bandwidth; 6) developing simulation codes that take into account radiation, absorption of photons, the finite temperature of the surrounding chambers, and the vacuum conditions.

The second part of the sixth session specifically reviewed the topic of crystalline beams. Here, Tobias Schaez from U Freiburg nostalgically recalled his Ph.D. time at PALLAS, LMU München, while reviewing the lessons, achievements, and problems. PALLAS operated in both continuous and synchrotron mode. Overcoming the “heating peak” required strong 3D cooling. Features of crystalline beams were described (Fig. 9). At PALLAS, a 2D zigzag crystal was rotating from the horizontal into the vertical plane by itself under the influence of shear forces. A static crystal survives for 90 s, while a 1D crystalline beam survived for 0.4 s. During the discussion, Tobias Schaez pointed out some open challenges of crystalline beams: A promising approach could be to start the crystalline beam in a bucket and then accelerate.

Figure 8: Concept of storage-ring based quantum computer (Kevin Brown).

Figure 9: Crystalline beam at PALLAS (Tobias Schaetz).

From SANDIA laboratories, Dan Stick discussed surface ion traps and compared them with 3D traps. Requirements for surface traps include the storage of ions over long periods (hours so tens of hours). Some technical details were presented, such as a 2D array trap with a backside loading hole, 300 V at ~ 50 MHz, and a ring of 624-micron radius, with 88+1 control electrodes. A critical challenge of these micro-structures is the pseudopotential defects, which require local correction and tangential compensation. A 7-hour ion lifetime has been shown, and the trapping of 360 ions with 10-micron spacing. The final discussion of this session focused on the utility of quantum computers for beam physics. The audience expressed a mixed answer to the question “where could this be useful?”, not pointing out a single clear target for accelerator physics. However, it was reiterated that crystalline beams in storage rings offer the potential to overcome fundamental limitations of present-day QC: The decoherence of an entangled state and the scalability to millions of qubits.

8. Advanced cooling and the Gamma Factory

The last session of the workshop (**Seventh Session**) addressed the topics of advanced cooling and the Gamma Factory. Danyal Winter of GSI presented the status of GSI laser cooling development. Laser cooling of stored coasting ion beams had first been demonstrated at TSR Heidelberg (1990) and ASTRID in Aarhus (1991). The difficulty of the method is that bunching the ion beam counteracts the laser force. Novel results of laser cooling for a bunched beam were presented. Finally, the laser cooling for SIS100 is becoming now a facility cast in concrete and steel (Fig. 10).

Alexey Petrenko of BINP discussed, in the context of the Gamma Factory, that beam cooling/heating is an effect of multi-turn laser-ion interaction. Laser cooling can stabilize the ion motion if properly used. Of interest is the transverse cooling via dispersive coupling. Bunch combination with cooling is then foreseen as for electron beams in presence of synchrotron radiation. Ion beam accumulation and cooling at the SPS before full stripping will be the fundamental test, which may also lead to laser

cooling as the path to the ultimate luminosity collider! The final presentation at the workshop was delivered by Aurélien Martens of IJCLab, who reported on the Gamma Factory. The GF community is formed around a concept developed by Mieczyslaw Witold Krasny and, quite outstandingly, publishes its advancements in the journal *Annalen der Physik* (the place of Einstein’s work). The presentation stressed that the GF may require dedicated collimators, crystals, or laser cooling. It also requires intense software development, integrated into the Xtrack package of programs. The Fabry-Perot resonator, accumulating 5 J pulse energy at 40 MHz, will provide a 200-kW laser pulse. The funding of a Proof of Principle experiment is now on the critical path for the Gamma Factory.

Figure 10: Experimental setup of laser cooling at the GSI ESR (Danyal Winters).

9. Final discussion and epilogue

The **final discussion** at ESRW22 revolved around the following questions: 1) Did the workshop miss any important storage ring topics? 2) Are storage-ring light sources reaching the “end of the road”? 3) What are the most promising paths forward? 4) Which existing storage rings could be reconfigured for new tasks and explorations? 5) Which new or additional test facilities are needed? The discussion explored these points, and Witek Krasny even participated from Geneva Airport, setting a new standard for global networking.

All presentations and more details can be found on the workshop website <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1096767/>.